

Shrinking Smart as a new planning concept: Benchmarking planning and policy responses to urban shrinkage and depopulation.

Bozhidar Ivanov
PhD Candidate, TU Kaiserslautern
RE-CITY: Reviving Shrinking Cities Project

Re-City Final conference “Shrinking Cities Revived!” 17.03.2022

Agenda

- Research questions
- Shrinkage conceptualization theory vs. practice
- Cases and methods
- Benchmarking framework and conclusions
- “Shrinking Smart” as a broader policy and planning framework
- “Shrinking Smart” as a spatial planning concept

Research questions

- How can the concept of "Shrinking Smart" be formulated, based on existing research on urban shrinkage and based on the way that urban shrinkage has been addressed within the European Union? Secondly, what can the new planning concept of "Shrinking Smart" encompass, what would be its scope and direction?
- Given the lack of clear boundaries and conceptual coherence of the "Shrinking Smart" label until now, what should be the structure of the new planning concept and how would it correspond to the variety of planning systems and approaches in the European Union and the variety of shrinkage contexts?
- How has the perception of urban shrinkage shaped the policy and planning approaches and solutions in specific shrinkage contexts in the European Union and how can this knowledge feed into the new planning concept?
- What are the applicable alternatives to implement "Shrinking Smart" in the future in the context of European Union?

Conceptual instability of shrinkage

Despite academic debates on shrinkage definition, perception of shrinkage in practice in the context of specific planning system plays a role in defining the approach to it.

Planning systems differences

- Highly centralized, spatially oriented planning with well-established planning culture and practice
- Centralized flexible planning intersecting with policy making
- Planning as a learning curve in an autonomous planning system in a quasi-federal setting intersecting with policy making

Three traditions of planning, collaborative perspective: spatial planning, regional/economic planning, policy making

Healey, Patsy. 2006. Collaborative planning: Shaping places in fragmented societies. 2. ed. Planning, environment, cities. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan

Shrinkage as a dynamic process implying future action:

*A ‘shrinking city’ can be defined as an urban area — a city, part of a city, an entire metropolitan area or a town — that has experienced population loss, economic downturn, employment decline and social problems as symptoms of a structural crisis. The term ‘urban shrinkage’ is used to stress the fact that this **phenomenon is a multidimensional process with multidimensional effects** and having economic, demographic, geographic, social and physical dimensions that not only **continue to evolve** as a result of new global and local realities, but also **influence theories and research** proffering diagnosis, prognosis and remedies. The term expands our understanding of ‘decline’ beyond the simple linear process that is generally understood to follow deindustrialization.*

Martinez-Fernandez, C., Ivonne Audirac, Sylvie Fol, and Emmanuele Cunningham-Sabot. 2012. “Shrinking Cities: Urban Challenges of Globalization.” International Journal of Urban and Regional Research 36 (2): 213–25. doi:10.1111/j.1468-2427.2011.01092.x.

Cases and methods

- Shrinkage-relevant policy and planning approaches, resulting in spatial and other interventions (implementation) in Bilbao (Spain) between 2000 and 2015
- Shrinkage-relevant policy and planning approaches, resulting in spatial and other interventions (implementation) in Leipzig (Germany) between 2000 and 2015
- National policy for regional population decline in the province of Zeeland (the Netherlands) since 2010

Conclusions planning process, policy substance, planning substance

Conclusions implementation
(spatial and economic development)

Benchmarking framework

Benchmarking framework created based on policy benchmarking literature – practice benchmarking.
The verification of the theoretical hypotheses and with empirical data creates the benchmarking categories.
Phases added in order to facilitate the analysis and for applicability purposes.
The following slides present some of the conclusions as part of the benchmarking.

Benchmarking framework

The verification of the theoretical hypotheses and with empirical data creates the benchmarking categories.

Phases added in order to facilitate the analysis and for applicability purposes.

The following slides present some of the conclusions as part of the benchmarking.

Benchmarking framework

The verification of the theoretical hypotheses and with empirical data creates the benchmarking categories.

Phases added in order to facilitate the analysis and for applicability purposes.

The following slides present some of the conclusions as part of the benchmarking.

Benchmarking framework

The verification of the theoretical hypotheses and with empirical data creates the benchmarking categories.

Phases added in order to facilitate the analysis and for applicability purposes.

The following slides present some of the conclusions as part of the benchmarking.

Benchmarking framework: Phase 1

Benchmarking perspective and categories/City or region	Bilbao	Leipzig	Zeeland
Justification and causal perspective			
Contextual factors	Territorial planning perspective European and global economic orientation Topographical characteristics (limited space) Flood risk Rehabilitation trend in Spanish cities High percentage of private property	Demographic transition (depopulation) National and European economic orientation Central national location Climate change	Regional depopulation National agenda Maintaining economic competitiveness Sustainability and digitalization
Shrinkage conceptualization	Economic transition with significant spatial effects (obsolete structures and vacancy)	(Irreversible) demographic decline with multifaceted negative effects on urban development, housing, quality of life and economy	Inevitable process of population loss with negative effects on quality of life and economy
Planning system			
Scope of local planning	City limits, Metropolitan area	City limits	
Intermediate planning level	Metropolitan area	Regional (West Saxony)	
Other institutions/levels involved	Autonomous community government (state I	State government, Federal government	Provincial government
Further administrative specifics	Financial autonomy of the Basque Country	Financial dependence on federal government	Financial dependence on national government

Main conclusions:

- Particular contextual factors need to be taken into account prior to identifying instruments for approaching shrinkage
- Achieving a common understanding of the effects of the phenomenon across actors is required
- Assessing the planning system and the available capacity to respond to shrinkage is important for the formulation of the appropriate instruments.

Benchmarking framework: Phase 2

Planning process		
Benchmarking perspective and categories/City or region	Bilbao	Leipzig
Involvement of citizens	Initially limited, evolving in time	Extensive, evolving in time. Involvement in decision making and action.
Involvement of stakeholders	Extensive (private and public stakeholders). Partnerships.	Extensive (private and public stakeholders)
Capacity for inquiry/research	Limited, evolving in time	Extensive, evolving in time.
Capacity for integrated planning	Moderate, evolving in time.	Extensive. Planning and policy integrated by design.

Main conclusions:

- “Shrinking Smart” as a planning process driver encompasses a wider participation by citizens and other stakeholders, including private entities.
- The participatory nature of such a process can contribute to improved civic engagement and indirectly to better democratic practices
- Planning should be evidence-based in order to act as a control mechanism for easy fixes (e.g. large scale projects)
- Planning under shrinking conditions should be integrated, attempting to efficiently achieve more than one objective in different planning and policy domains.

Benchmarking framework: Phase 3 Policy

City or region		Bilbao		Leipzig		Zeeland		
DOMINANT NORMATIVE ORIENTATION		Improved urban image, global competitiveness, urban quality, quality of life.		Integrated approach to issues. Quality of life. National and regional economic centrality.		Maintain economic profile. Maintain quality of life and service provisioning. Efficiency.		
Benchmarking category	Thematic mapping	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation	Policy substance	Normative orientation	
Policy instruments	Economy and labour market	New industrial zones and business parks	New space for economic activity			Targeted policy support for existing companies	Maintain economic profile	
						Education and labour market coordination	Labour market accessibility. Counteract labour market shortages.	
		Reskilling programmes. Educational infrastructure.	Overcoming social exclusion Attract talent		Dependent on state and federal policy	Cross-border agreements	Labour market accessibility. Counteract labour market shortages.	
	Economy and space	Flagship regeneration projects	Image - global competitiveness and attractiveness	Demand-oriented spatial offer for economic activities	Competitiveness			
				Reuse of obsolete space	Avoid sprawl and promote compact development			
	Urban settlements and regional development. Quality of life.					Financial instruments	Liveability improvement	
	Housing	Price controlled housing provisioning	Housing accessibility. Strict control on market-led housing construction	Programme for urban redevelopment - housing demolition and renovation	Quality of life improvement Image & attractiveness	Housing and neighbourhood renovation.	Regional agreements on service provisioning	Service provisioning
				Financial programme for social issues in vulnerable districts	Promote social inclusion	Housing restructuring projects.	Combat housing vacancy Ensure housing market functioning Quality of life improvement	
Social issues	Areas of integrated rehabilitation (ARI) - district specific	Improvement of housing conditions, urban quality and overcoming social issues						

Main conclusions:

Growth orientation is pervasive. Quality of life can be pursued in parallel to growth but needs to be scrutinized.

Benchmarking framework: Phase 3 Planning

City or region		Bilbao		Leipzig	
DOMINANT NORMATIVE ORIENTATION		Improved urban image, global competitiveness, urban quality, quality of life		Integrated approach to issues. Quality of life. National and regional economic centrality	
Benchmarking category	Thematic mapping	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation
Planning instruments	Urban blight and deterioration	Revitalization and regeneration (incl. reuse of obsolete space)	New space for economic activity Image - global competitiveness and attractiveness	Revitalization measures	Quality of life improvement Image & attractiveness
	Land use	Limits to developable land	Land use efficiency	Municipal land allocation to investors	Active management of obsolete industrial space
		Zoning: land use function, regimes of use, strict regulation, sanctions.	Balanced/mixed use of land, economic diversification, just use of space Market control (high private property)		Counteract land vacancy
	Greening and public space	District specific interventions	Green and public space connectivity	Temporary land use. New green areas.	Green space connectivity
	New construction	Limitations and strict rules	Market control. Avoid speculation.	Active district-led planning	Demand-oriented construction
	Socially disadvantaged areas and district-specific interventions		Address specific area needs incl. social issues *Special plans deliver the interventions from the government programme for Areas of Integrated Rehabilitation	District-specific interventions & dedicated programmes	Overcoming social issues Promote economic activity Quality of life improvement
		Special plans for key areas and districts	Large-scale urban regeneration	Local integrated plans	Integrated objectives-blurring boundaries *Local integrated plans deliver the interventions from the government programme for socially disadvantaged areas
	Housing	Renovation and accessibility investment	Improve housing conditions	Housing market resizing	Counteract housing vacancy Improve quality of housing Ensure market functioning Housing accessibility
	Large-scale urban regeneration	Property consolidation in key areas	Efficient implementation (fragmented property)		

Main conclusions:

- Possible instruments depend on a number of factors, namely planning culture (market-led vs. controlled development) and land and building stock ownership (private vs. public).
- Different instruments, depending on the factors need to be utilized

Benchmarking framework: Phase 3 Spatial and economic development

City or region		Bilbao		Leipzig		Zeeland	
DOMINANT NORMATIVE ORIENTATION		Improved urban image, global competitiveness, urban quality, quality of life.		Integrated approach to issues. Quality of life. National and regional economic centrality.		Maintain economic profile. Maintain quality of life and service provisioning. Efficiency.	
Benchmarking category	Thematic mapping	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation	Policy substance	Normative orientation
Spatial development	Overall orientation	Normative orientation		Normative orientation		Normative orientation	
		Densification (limited space)		Densification (counteract extensive sprawl)			
	Land use approach	Compact development		Counteract land and industrial vacancy			
		Mixed use		Mixed use			
		Greening & public space expansion on district level		Greening (incl. large-scale projects)			
	Building stock	Building rehabilitation & preservation of cultural heritage		Building rehabilitation & preservation of cultural heritage			
	Infrastructure (railway)	Railway optimization - internal and external mobility; reuse of space		Railway optimization - internal and external mobility; reuse of space			
Environmental considerations	Environmental sustainability, reuse of materials		Climate change adaptation (incl. energy efficiency)				
Economic development	Overall orientation	Growth-oriented		Growth-oriented		Growth-oriented	
	Migration	Attracting migration		Attracting migration		Attracting migration	
	Existing economy	Preserve industry		Develop endogenous economic potential		Preserve existing economic profile.	
	New economy	Tertiary global competitiveness. Culture. Tourism.		Regional, national, European competitiveness. Knowledge economy. Culture.		Adapt industry to new global conditions	
	Private capital	Key role of private capital		Private ownership of housing - involvement		Key role of private capital	
	Non-traditional economic ideas	Circularity				Greening of industry, circularity, supply chain agreements, renewable energy, green hydrogen	

Main conclusions: no justification on spatial expansion of cities. Depending on the geographical, topographical and overall spatial setting, shrinking cities ought to pursue **compact development** and **densification**. This would encourage the reutilization of lots and buildings, handling vacancy and obsolete space and overall increase the efficiency of space use. By targeting compact development and further densification cities ought to explore **mixed use** developments, incorporating residential, commercial and **public** uses of space. The latter can also be supported by targeted interventions in **greening**.

Benchmarking framework: Phase 3 Actors

City or region	Bilbao		Leipzig		Zeeland	
DOMINANT NORMATIVE ORIENTATION	Improved urban image, global competitiveness, urban quality, quality of life.		Integrated approach to issues. Quality of life. National and regional economic centrality.		Maintain economic profile. Maintain quality of life and service provisioning. Efficiency.	
Benchmarking category	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation	Policy and planning substance	Normative orientation	Policy substance	Normative orientation
Institutional actors	Higher autonomy of the Basque Country Basque Government, Bilbao Municipality, local executive agencies (e.g. SURBISA, BilbaoRia2000), RENFE Spanish Railways, Port authority		Federal system and partial state autonomy Federal government, Saxony State Government, Regional Planning Authority West Saxony, Leipzig Municipality, District management agencies, Deutsche Bahn German Railways		Higher dependence on national government National government, Zeeland Provincial Government, Zeeland Municipalities	
Non-institutional actors	Public-private management commission (e.g. Zorrotzaurre), local citizen councils, strategy quangos (e.g. Bilbao Metropoli-30), private owners, companies, local business networks		Housing companies, local citizen initiatives		Regional expert and citizen working groups, regional business networks	

Main conclusions:

- Partnership and coordination between different levels of the planning system is required
- Private actors involvement is important but is also a potential risk, depending on the context.

“Shrinking Smart” planning concept – broader policy and planning framework

A policy and planning effort under the conditions of urban shrinkage or depopulation on regional scale where the long-term projections indicate a population decline.

Based on an informed assessment of the effects of the phenomenon, specific contextual characteristics and planning system capacity, planners and policy makers **commit to manage the consequences of shrinkage** in a coordinated effort across the levels of the planning system which may involve planning and policy instruments originating and encompassing different scales.

The planners and policy makers **may or may not accept the long-term population decline**, however, this does not affect their commitment to manage the consequences of shrinkage taking into account the **economic effects**, attempting to address the **quality of life** of the remaining citizens and to address existing **social and service provisioning challenges**.

Based on the normative decision in the above areas, planners and policy makers decide **to accept the long-term population decline and manage shrinkage; not accept the long term population decline and manage shrinkage but eventually pursue regrowth; or focus only on managing the effects of the phenomenon**. In either of the options, the planners and policy makers attempt a **balance between economic considerations and quality of life** considerations. The decision is formulated with a **perspective for the future** with a coherent idea to guide the long-term planning and policy efforts and this idea may also have specific image implications.

Potential applicability of the framework

Preliminary normative stance			Commitment to manage shrinkage		
Population decline acceptance			Accept (stable or declining population)	Not accept (stable population, ready to regrow)	Indifferent
Factors					
Image implications and dominant normative orientation	Political appeal and discretion		The Citadel: a good place to live (Commitment to adapt to shrinkage and to improve quality of life at least on par with economic considerations)	The Aspiring Phoenix: regrowing stronger (Commitment to manage shrinkage but willing to regrow economically with improved quality of life for remaining and future citizens)	The Lifeboat: a safe place (Managing available resources and attempting to sustain economically and in terms of quality of life)
PLANNING OR POLICY DOMAIN					
Economy	Growth pervasiveness. Existing endogenous economic potential. Existing industry dependence. Regional economic structure.	Pursue growth	Enable/not impede endogenous small scale businesses Preserve existing industries Ready to grow but not actively working on it Regional: smart specialisation, clusters, networks	Preserve existing businesses and industries Actively attract external investment Actively develop endogenous potential Regional: smart specialisation, clusters, networks; actively attract investment	Preserve existing business and industry
		Pursue stabilization or not actively growth	Preserve existing endogenous small scale businesses Speculatively small scale heterodox approaches (e.g. degrowth) Dependent on regional/national context	Preserve existing businesses and industries	Preserve existing endogenous small scale businesses Speculatively small scale heterodox approaches (e.g. degrowth) Dependent on regional/national context
Quality of life	Existing understanding and importance of the topic. Planning culture.		Improve	Improve	Maintain
Social issues and service provisioning. Technical and social infrastructure.	Population structure and needs. Existing social challenges. Inequality and segregation. Condition and accessibility of technical and social infrastructure.		Social measures. Adapt services and optimize infrastructure to existing population. Regional connectivity (technical and transport) and service provisioning (technical and social)	Adapt services and infrastructure to existing population. Ready to provide services and infrastructure for newcomers. Service accessibility and social cohesion risks (tradeoffs existing and future inhabitants). Regional connectivity (technical and transport) and optimize service provisioning (technical and social). Competition risks.	Ensure services and infrastructure for existing population. Social measures desirable. Regional connectivity (technical and transport) and optimize service provisioning (technical and social)

“Shrinking Smart” planning concept – spatial perspective

A concept that guides efforts in spatial planning under conditions of declining population where, depending on the geographical, topographical and overall spatial setting, a shrinking city pursues **compact development** and **densification**. This would encourage the reutilization of lots and buildings, handling vacancy and obsolete space and overall increased efficiency of land use. By targeting compact development and further densification the city encourages **mixed use** developments, incorporating residential, commercial and **public** uses of space. The latter can also be supported by targeted interventions in **greening**.

Preliminary spatial normative stance			Compact development, densification, mixed use, public space, greening. Regional connectivity and coordination.
Planning or policy domain	Factors	Specific objective	Planning instruments
Overall spatial development	<i>Market-driven</i>	Impose control, limit unregulated activity, return to city limits	Spatial expansion limitations, stricter zoning, sanctions, regimes of use, well-maintained ownership databases/cadastral data, public-private partnerships, regional spatial management
	<i>Controlled</i>	Actively manage and intervene in urban space within city limits	Proactive allocation of developable land, public funded regeneration projects, flexible planning instruments (e.g. temporary use, reuse)
New construction	<i>Market-driven</i>	Actively manage new construction	Stricter zoning, mixed use incentives, public-private partnerships, regional coordination of new construction (avoid competition)
	<i>Controlled</i>	Encourage mixed use	Mixed use incentives, public funded regeneration projects
Land use	<i>Private ownership</i>	Partner with owners	Public-private partnerships, flexible planning instruments (e.g. temporary use, reuse, regimes), sanctions, compensation mechanisms
	<i>Public ownership</i>	Actively manage land use	Public funded regeneration projects, flexible planning instruments (e.g. temporary use, reuse), proactive allocation of land, ownership transfer between public owners, land banks, backup development lands
Existing building stock	<i>Private ownership</i>	Encourage reuse and maintenance. Impose control.	Instruments and stimuli (incl. expert and financial) for rehabilitation, energy efficiency, cultural heritage preservation, reuse and maintenance.
	<i>Public ownership</i>	Reuse and maintenance	Public-led programmes, projects, instruments and initiatives for rehabilitation, energy efficiency, cultural heritage preservation, reuse and maintenance.

Zabalburu station Bilbao – one of the last deep railway trenches separating two neighbourhoods, to be regraded and submerged

TV Ad, Zeeland

Vacancy under development Bayerischer Bahnhof, Leipzig

"The experience we have [...] is that without development, without economic development, there is no rehabilitation."

Interview with an expert from local agency, Bilbao

"I think it was clear after 2002 that European funding [and other administrative and financial support] is only given when there is a collaboration between these different roles in city-society: politics, administration, citizens and associations"

Interview with a district manager, Leipzig

"You know that we are more involved and they are and I think that's the best thing. Don't give only money, but also involvement, together to build some new knowledge and everything you need to adapt those issues with population decline."

Interview with a national expert, the Netherlands